

GUIDANCE AND COUNSELLING IN EFFECTIVE TEACHING AND LEARNING IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN NIGERIA

BY

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Abstract

Development of a child can only take place in an environment conducive for teaching and learning. It is in realization of the above that all educational services which can promote teaching and learning in schools are given prominent attention by educational planners. Counselling services in school develop, assess and improve educational programmes, enhance teaching and improve the competence of the teacher and reduce cost for the children. Therefore, this paper aims on the need for effective counselling services in secondary schools. Consequently, this paper seeks to examine the concept of counselling, the different counselling services like educational, vocational and socio/persona services, the various problems facing guidance and counselling as it affects teaching and learning in Secondary schools. Finally, the paper recommended among others that individuals be made to understand, appreciate and accept guidance and counselling services in secondary schools because of the roles they play in effective teaching and learning process.

Keywords: Guidance and Counselling, Teaching, Learning and School

Introduction

These two words generally take on different meanings. The former refers to helping students' whole-person development, while the latter is frequently targeted at helping students with problems. In other words, guidance work is preventive and developmental in nature whereas counselling is more of supportive, remedial work (LaiYeung, 2014). The global trend seems to have moved from a casework and remedial approach to a preventive, developmental approach in providing guidance and counselling (Lai-Yeung, 2014). Hence guidance and counselling are a very necessary therapy to school children. According to Oviogbodu (2015), counselling can be defined as a number of procedures in assisting an individual to solve his problems. Counselling is more involved emotionally in the affective realm personalized learning, that is, emotions and feelings,

values, attitudes. Counselling is an interaction or relationship between two or few individuals, the client counsellor relationship on trust (Adebowale, 2012; cited in Oviogbodu, 2015).

Guidance and counselling is an important educational tool for shaping a student's orientation from the negative ideas that is planted in it by his/her peers to the positive and more rewarding ones. Okon (2010) defined guidance as total programme of a number of highly specialized activities implemented by specialist to help an individual to make wise decision. It can also be defined as a process designed in other to assist an individual to decide what he/she wants to do and how best to do it in order to yield a positive result. Hence, the need for the school counsellor is to assist every child by moulding their future through counselling therapy. The school counsellor is seen as a role model and highly respected by students. The counsellors by their training are expected to be friends with the school child, listen to the child's complaints, short comings and proffer guidance to the child in a quest of moulding the child in the right part to take in their life pursuit. Egbo (2013) stated that "the total development of a child can only take place in an environment conducive for teaching and learning". It is in realization of the above that all educational services which can promote teaching and learning in schools are given prominent attention by educational planners. Consequent on the above unmistakable affirmation, counselling services are indispensable for students' academic achievements and future career success.

Counselling services are among the school educational services. It is believed that guidance and counselling services in school shall develop, assess and improve educational programmes; enhance teaching and improve the competence of the teacher and reduce cost for the children. School children are undergoing some of the most difficult periods in their teaching/learning and future life endeavors. The transition from childhood to adulthood is a difficult one, even for the most balanced child. Apart from the influence of the family, the other major influence on the young person's life is the school and the school environment. The most that other influences can attempt to do is to help each young person to cope with the changes and wrought associated with adolescence, to develop a sense of responsibility, to make definite and considerable personal decisions. Nonetheless, families and schools have a duty in assisting young people in their self-growth towards becoming a self-fulfilled and well-adjusted adult. The schools in their bid, can offer this all-important assistance through effective guidance and counselling provisions.

Guidance and counselling according to Akinade (2012), is a process of helping an individual become fully aware of himself/herself and the way in which he/she is responding to the influences of the environment. It further assists the child to establish some personal meaning for this behavior and to develop and classify a set of goals and value for future behavior.

Counselling on the other hand, is a learning process in which a counsellor helps an individual or individuals learn, understand themselves and their environment and be in a position to choose the right type of behaviours that will help them develop, grow, progress, ascend, mature and set up educationally, vocationally and socio-personally (Egbo, 2013). In other words, counselling is a transformative process that aims at helping individuals gain understanding of themselves and learn all that are to be learnt both in and outside the school. Thus, counselling remains an invaluable means of promoting effective teaching/learning process. It helps the students in mitigating their learning challenges thereby equipping them with the necessary coping skills and study tips for academic and career success. Okoye (2010) stated that the main aim of teaching is to help someone acquire or change some skills, attitude, knowledge, idea or appreciation. In other words, it is to bring about some desirable changes in the learners. She further noted that teaching is said to be effective only when the learners have been able to achieve the set behavioural objectives. In the same vein, Nnabuike (2012) stressed that a teacher is also a learner because there is no end to learning.

Learning in this instance, is viewed as the mental activity by which knowledge and skills, habits and attitudes, virtues and ideas are acquired, retained and utilized resulting in the progressive adoption and modification of conduct and behaviour (Okoye, 2010). In this regard, the work of teacher is to help students to learn through deliberate and conscious manipulation of information, knowledge, skill, values, attitudes and habits of learners in order to bring about learning, leading to desirable change in character (Nnabuike, 2012). Based on the above, no effective teaching could be said to have taken place if learning has not occurred. Regrettably, in most secondary school, most teachers are cheating instead of teaching. Some do not know the methods for teaching and so do not make positive impact. Some teachers do not care about the students under their care instead they engage in petty trading and farming abandoning the job for which they are being paid. It is also possible that one could put his effort to teach and yet some students will still fail to learn, this is where counselling comes in for there are student who find it difficult to learn due to some learning problems. Some do not understand why they are in school and what is expected of them.

Counselling is a learning process in which a counsellor helps an individual or individuals learn, understand themselves and their environment and be in a position to choose the right behaviours that will help them develop, grow, progress, ascend, mature and step up, educationally, vocationally and socio personally, (Egbo, 2013). In other words, counselling is a transformative process of helping people to learn all that are to be learnt both in and outside the School. Counselling is a person-to-person process in which one person is helped by another to develop, increase in understanding and ability to solve his or her problems. Sometimes it could involve a

group of two or more persons. Consequent on the above points, it is important to highlight the benefits of guidance and counselling to students in the school programme.

School Guidance Counsellors' Areas of Work Towards Engendering Effective Teaching/Learning

The school guidance and counselors' area of work in the schools are as follows;

1. Orientation service: This is designed to assist students adjust adaptively when found in new school environment for effective learning. The teachers should also be given orientation on how to handle the learners from time to time.
2. Information service: This service is designed to provide students with data about educational, social and vocational opportunities. It involves collection of data for clients/students.
3. Appraisal service: Appraisal involves the collection, administration, interpretation and clinical usage of variety of test devices in order to provide effective counselling services to students. (Akinade, 2012).
4. Placement service: The goal of this service is to ensure that students achieve placement whether on programme of the study, a career, work study or even a medical treatment programme.

5. Follow-up, research or evaluation service: The goal of this service is to provide feedback on the effectiveness of school guidance through research into the concrete outcomes of the school guidance.
6. Referral service: This is sending a client to another person or agency for assistance where the counsellor is unable to solve the problem and when there is need of other specialist the counsellor do referral. The counsellor does not claim to know everything and so the need for referral to other needs of the students.
7. Counselling service: counselling service is the interaction between a client and counsellor that aims at solving or understanding the client's problems the more. This interaction enhances effective teaching and learning.
8. Teachers Forum: The Teachers Forum is meant to gather all the teachers in the school to discuss teacher/students problems (Teaching and Learning). The programme is used to organize the teachers, educate and direct them on how to improve on their skills, ability and method of teaching to enhance effective teaching and learning. During the staff forum, the counsellor uses either the principal or vice- principal or other teachers as resource persons who will help to talk to the teachers.

Guidance and counselling services when rendered as it should be rendered in the schools bearing in mind the national goals of education will no doubt go a long way in ensuring effective teaching and learning in schools.

The school guidance and counselors' areas of works therefore, is the bedrock on which effective teaching/learning in secondary schools can be situated. It will assist students to adjust adequately in their new school environment, furnish them with requisite data about educational, social and vocational opportunities within their society and help them to solve or understand their learning difficulties. These areas of work as covered by school guidance counsellors will prepare a fertile ground for effective teaching/learning to take root and thrive in secondary schools. Hence, the need to accord the needed attention the general aims of guidance and counselling in promoting effective teaching/learning in secondary schools.

Aims of Guidance and Counselling Services in Promoting effective Teaching/Learning In Secondary Schools

The aims of guidance and counselling service in schools is to assist the student in fulfilling his/her basic physiological needs, understanding themselves and developing associations with peers, balancing between permissiveness and controls in the school setting, realizing successful achievement, and providing opportunities to gain independence (Heyden, 2011). The purpose of guidance and counselling therefore provides emphasis and strength to educational programs. Some specific aims of the school guidance and counselling program includes the following (Gibson, 2009 cited in Lunenburg, 2010):

I. To Provide for the Realization of Student Potentialities: To all students, the school offers a wide choice of courses and co-curricular activities. A significant function of education is to help

students identify and develop their potentialities. The counsellor's role is to assist students to

distribute their energies into the many learning opportunities available to them. Every student needs help in planning his major course of study and pattern of co-curricular activities.

II. To Help Children with Developing Problems: Even those students who have chosen an appropriate educational program for themselves may have problems that require help. A teacher may need to spend from one fifth to one-third of his time with a few pupils who require a great deal of help, which deprives the rest of the class from the teacher's full attention to their needs. The counsellor, by helping these youngsters to resolve their difficulties, frees the classroom teacher to use his time more efficiently.

III. To Contribute to the Development of the School's Curriculum: Counsellors, in working with individual students, know their personal problems and aspirations, their talents and abilities, as well as the social pressures confronting them. Counsellors, therefore, can provide data that serve as a basis for curriculum development, and they can help curriculum developers shape courses of study that more accurately reflect the needs of students. Too often, counsellors are not included in curriculum development efforts.

IV. To Provide Teachers with Technical Assistance: Pre-service teacher training institutions typically provide very limited experience with the more technical aspects of guidance work. Thus, a need exists in most schools for assistance with guidance and counselling functions essential to the educational program. Specifically, the guidance counsellor is qualified to assist teachers with selecting, administering, and interpreting tests; selecting and using cumulative, anecdotal, and other types of records; providing help and suggestions relative to counselling techniques, which teachers can use in counselling their students; and providing leadership in developing and conducting professional development of teachers in guidance functions.

V. To contribute to the Mutual Adjustment of Students and the School: Guidance has

a responsibility for developing and maintaining a cooperative relationship between students and the school. Teachers and counsellors must be cognizant of students' needs. Students also must make adjustments to the school. They have a responsibility to contribute something to the school. A major contribution of students is that of making appropriate use of the school's resources and working toward accomplishments. Such mutual adjustment of students and school is facilitated by providing suggestions for program improvements, conducting research for educational improvements, contributing to students' adjustment through counselling, and fostering wholesome school-home attitudes.

Effective Teaching and Learning Process, Guidance and Counselling Perspective

Teaching is a common phenomenon in school; it is aimed at bringing about a positive change in the life of an individual. In the context of guidance and counselling, the counsellor listens to the child's problem, extract the issue before him/her and try as much as possible to help the child in overcoming the problem through proper advice and continue engagement/follow up to see if the child is applying the therapy. Teacher effectiveness in use of instructional resources is considered important to enable them master the requisite knowledge of the subject matter content and enhance their teaching capabilities (Orodho, 2013, 2014). To retain efficient and experienced workforce in an organization such as, a school set up is very crucial to the standard organization. Teachers subject matter knowledge, teaching capability among others are leading factors in teaching effectiveness. Effective teachers understand and are able to apply strategies to help students increase in the academic achievement and also help learners cope. According to Abolade (2000), as cited in Egbo, (2013) teaching is described as a set of activities that are designed to bring about changes in the behaviour of learners. Popham (2010) sees teaching as explaining, demonstrating, guiding and counselling by the teacher in order to effect a change in the learner. Conversely, Okoye (2010) stated that the main aim of teaching is to help someone acquire or change some skills, attitude, knowledge, idea or appreciation. In other words, it is to bring about some desirable changes in the learners, she also noted that teaching is said to be effective only when the learners have been able to achieve the set behavioural objectives. Nnabuike, (2012) believes that a teacher is also a learner because there is no end to learning

Learning is therefore, the mental activity by which knowledge and skills, habits and attitudes, virtues and ideas are acquired, retained and utilized resulting in the progressive adoption and modification of conduct and behaviour (Okoye, 2010). Similarly, Oketch (2012) sees learning as the acquisition of new behaviour or a change in behaviour whether positive or negative change. It also includes acquisition of knowledge, information, skills and cultures. He therefore noted that learning definitely will lead to change in one's thought, patterns and feeling. Learning also involves cognitive process especially mental reasoning. Thus teaching and learning go together; it is like buying and selling. If nobody learns it follows that nobody teaches. Nnabuike (2012) noted that the work of the teacher is to help students to learn through deliberate and conscious manipulation of information, knowledge, skill, values, attitudes and habits of the learners in order to bring about learning, leading to desirable changes in character. Based on the above, no effective teaching could be said to have taken place if learning has not occurred.

The teacher in a classroom condition act as a counsellor in the form of Teaching Advisory Programme (TAP); in the light of this situation the teacher counsel the students in the right direction to take using life instance and experience to act of a guide since the students already see him/her as a role model. Effective teachers should have a thorough knowledge of their subject content and skill. Through this, they inspire in their students a love of learning. They also

understand how students' best learn concepts, content and skills. Effective teachers use their knowledge of learning processes to determine which will be most effective to help the particular students in their classes to learn successfully. They should provide a safe and orderly environment, both physically and emotionally, so students can achieve their potential. They know students learn best if they are in a class room where they feel safe and confident to attempt new tasks even if at first they are unsure about how to tackle them. Effective teachers are in the habit of constantly reflecting on how well they are getting through to their students and searching for better ways of teaching those who are not responding as well as extending those who are achieving well.

The implication for guidance and counselling is that the teacher observes the students during and after the class. The teacher also evaluates the students to know the extent they have gone in assimilating the subject matter they have been taught and to ascertain if there is any need for counselling based on this exercise. More so, the teacher may also wish to invite the counsellor to the class for general class discussion or refer a particular student that is deficient to the counsellor's office for guidance section. In this instance, the guidance and counsellor acts as a conduit to both the teachers and their students towards promoting effective teaching/learning processes in secondary schools

Problems Facing Guidance and Counselling service Provision in schools

The main aim of guidance and counselling is to assist the student to develop physically, mentally, emotionally, morally and educationally to cope with the learning situations within and outside the school environment. Some of these services provided by counsellors are hindered because of the following problems;

- a. Lack of trained counsellors: Despite the fact that there are many holders of higher degrees in guidance and counselling in Nigeria today, not as many are qualified to be real counsellors because they lack the skills necessary for the practice. There is limited number of trained counsellors in Nigerian schools and the ones already trained choose to go into non-school settings (Akinade 2012).

- b. Doubt about the efficacy of guidance and counselling: Some people such as uninitiated colleagues, teachers, principals or administrators doubt the efficacy of counselling. They are skeptical about reliance on its use.
- c. Lack of commitment of Government officers: Ogunyemi (2003) as cited in Egbo 2013 noted that although the federal Government entrenched the guidance and counselling programme in the NPE (1981), there is still much to do when it comes to practical support and its implementation. He noted that more committed action will help the growth of the profession.
- d. Lack of or inadequate funding: Guidance and counselling is not well funded today, the education enterprise has become a costly venture. Enough funds are not allocated to each school to run its various services. Where funds are available, very little is earmarked for counselling purposes. It seems the various levels of government (Federal, state and Local) do not want to stretch their budgets with extra demands from emerging unit such as guidance and counselling, yet it is known that effective counselling demands adequate funding to purchase items such as psychological tests, journals and various publications, play gadgets, cardboards and various felt pens as well as money to organize activities such as Orientation, Excursions, career clubs and Career Day/week and furnishing a counsellor's office.
- e. Confidentiality: Clients expect that their secrets or privileged information be kept secret or confidential and not exposed to others. However, referrals agents such as teachers, peers, parents, principals among others expect counsellors to divulge such information to them. Failure of the counsellor to reveal the "secret" may raise the degree of suspicion of his activities. Revealing the secrets lead to loss of faith in counselling and counsellors on one part will lose clients. Yet all these are happening.

(Akinade 2012)

- f. Counsellors created problems: Counsellors also create major problems to guidance and counselling delivery. Some are not fully committed to the counselling profession. Instead of being serious minded in their counselling duties, some join in the staff room discussions.
- g. Feeling of suspicion of the role/of integrity of counsellors: Some school personnel still see the counsellor as having a “hidden agenda” or something to hide when a client goes into the counselling room (where this is available) some give counsellors negative or derogatory labels. This is more so where the other workers doubt the moral integrity of counsellors who give individual counselling to young ones. This feeling becomes more serious when a male counsellor treats female students and gives the interaction high confidentiality.
- h. Blurred role of the guidance counsellor: Several people in the society do not know the specific roles of the counsellor. Even in the school settings, where awareness is expected to be high, school personnel such as teachers and principals do not understand or they misconstrue the functions of the counsellors.

Conclusion

Guidance and counsellors is of paramount importance in effective teaching and learning in schools in Nigeria and globally. Counsellors are transformers, reformers in educational, vocational and socio-personal issues surrounding students academic activities, achievements, successful career choices and development in every society. Guidance and counselling is tinted toward preventing the child from indulging in negative vices and helping the child to choose the right parts in life to be successful in the pursuit of future ambition. It is necessary that the counsellor build the confidence of the child to trust him/her to be able to give him/her the rightful information needed in these helping roles. This is so, because, client that trust counsellors normally open up with vital information to their counsellors which may enable the client to introduce any other person with counselling need to the counsellor.

Guidance and counselling service in schools is to assist the student in fulfilling his/her basic physiological needs, understanding themselves and developing associations with peers, balancing between permissiveness and controls in the school setting, realizing successful achievement, and providing opportunities to gain independence. Therefore guidance and counselling no doubt has a lot of roles to play for effective teaching and learning and therefore deserves maximum support of everybody.

Recommendations

Based on the salient points highlighted in this paper, the following recommendations are proffered:

i. There is need for adequate enlightenment on the part of the public to accept guidance and counselling. This will help develop strategies for school administrators and teachers to achieve a realistic perception of students in their school environment. ii. Government should support guidance and counselling practically by providing and making funds available for all the services in guidance and counselling.

iii. Schools should periodically evaluate school counsellors from the feedback of the students they counselled from time to time with the objective of encouraging them to do better job of guiding and counselling as well. iv. The guidance counsellor should be made to attend his/her professional conferences to learn new ideas of therapies with clients.

v. Parents also should be included in guidance and counselling programme through giving them progressive report of their children and occasionally organize parents and guidance forum. vi. Counsellors should understand their limits in helping the students and therefore make use of referrals.

References

Abiri, J.O ., (1977): "A Sample Study of Nigerian Adolescents' Academic and Occupational Aspirations". West African Journal of Educational and Vocational Measurement, Vol. 14, No. 1, August.

Avent, Catherine, (1967): Which Career? Robert Hale London, pp. 10 - 12. Durojaiye, M.O.A ., (1970): "School Education and Occupational Choice: Social Psychological Research in Nigerian International Secondary School" West African Journal of Education, Vol. 14.

National Policy on Education (1977): Federal Government Press, Lagos.

National Policy on Education (1981): Federal Government Press, Lagos.

Okeke, A.N ., (1973): " Impact of School Subjects on Choice of Occupation and Profession: West African Journal of Education, Vol. 17, pp. 5 11.

Olayinka, M.S ., (1973): "Job Aspirations of Youths and the Educational Provision in Lagos". West African Journal of Education, Vol. 17, No. 1

Olayinka, M.S ., (1980): "Career Guide". Unpublished monograph, Faculty.